

QUIZ**LAST NAME: KYENDREBEOGO****FIRST NAME: JESSICA****PROGRAM CODE: MBAIO****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. How to properly cite an author or source?

- By the use of in-text citation and list of works cited.¹**
- Provide the references.
- Providing the author's in parenthesis.
- By the use of just a footnote.

2. When is a style guide essential?

- If the finished publication is to be coherent and consistent.²**
- They are internationally recognized.
- It establishes the author's brand identity.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2019), 11.

² Ibid., 29.

It is recommended by the publisher.

3. **Which of the following is wrong about writing process steps?**

Selecting.³

Prewriting.

Editing.

Publishing.

4. **Which one of the following is a primary source?**

Interview.⁴

Television.

Encyclopedia.

Journal article.

5. **What is a working hypothesis?**

A promising answer.⁵

A plausible answer.

An evidence.

Data collected.

³ Patrick Sebranek, Kemper Dave, and Meyer Verne. *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning*. (Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 15.

⁴ Ibid., 263.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 21.

6. **When do we not need to provide a citation?**

- When you express your ideas, theories, arguments, conclusions.**⁶
- When you quote exact words from a source.
- When you paraphrase ideas that are associated with a specific source, even if you don't quote exact words from it.
- When you use any idea, data, or method attributable to any source you consulted.

7. **What is firstly provided in a book reference?**

- Author.**⁷
- Publication date.
- Book title.
- Book edition.

8. **Which one is a tricky word?**

- Judgement.**⁸
- Medieval.
- Professor.
- Archbishop.

⁶ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 4* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2020), 57.

⁷ Ibid., 59.

⁸ Ibid., 97.

9. Which English is used by the European Commission?

- British English.**⁹
- American English.
- American and British English.
- Canadian English.

10. Which one is not an acronym?

- BBC.**¹⁰
- Benelux.
- Radar.
- NATO.

⁹ European Commission. 7th ed. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission* (Brussels: Directorate-General for Translation, 2011), 5.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 26.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.